

EVALUATION OF BUILDING PROJECT ABANDONMENT IN ENUGU URBAN

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Abstract: *This study focused on Evaluation of building project abandonment in Enugu urban. The aim of this research is to evaluate the building project abandonment in Enugu urban. The specific objectives are; to identify the cumulative factors responsible for public building projects abandonment in Enugu urban; to assess the challenges of construction project abandonment in the Nigerian Construction industry. The survey research design was used for the study. The targeted respondents are the contractors, client/public and Engineers whereas the total population of the study is 245. The sample size 193 was gotten through Tarro Yamane formula. The data collected through structured questionnaire was analyzed using spss statistical package which was turned to tables and simple percentage approach. The findings of the study reveals that cumulative factors responsible for the cumulative factors responsible for public project abandonment in Enugu urban includes lack of fund, inconsistent government policies, lack of accountabilities, high level of corruption, incompetent contractors, non-availability of building materials, lack of utilities, wrong materials, lack of infrastructural facilities, poor planning and undefined contracts. The study further indicates that the highest ranking factor is the lack of fund and lowest ranking factor is the ineffective change control. More so, the study indicates that the challenges confronting construction project abandonment in the Nigerian construction industry includes technical knowledge, promoting corruption and embezzlement of public/private fund, loss of asset utilization, loss of finance, it discourages innovation and encourages risk transfer. The study recommends that there is need for government and relevant stakeholder in the industries to enforce the application of integrated value and risk management in order to reduce/minimize the rate of project abandonment in Nigeria specifically in Enugu urban.*

Introduction

Construction industry all over the world has not been static and the reasons for this include clients' growing demand, complexity of

construction projects, advancement in technology and introduction of new innovations (Oke, 2024). Project abandonment is a global challenge but a country like United Kingdom and

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other European countries are continually modernizing their Construction Industry in order to minimise the endemic effects on the construction industry. In the United Kingdom, the Modernizing Construction Report (MCR, 2021) was an improvement of on the two other Committees set up by the Government of United Kingdom on modernizing Construction: "Construction Team" by Latham (1994) and "Rethinking Construction" by Egan (1998). These reports used to formulate the Construction Regulations and Standards instituted in United Kingdom. While in Nigeria, it's unfortunate, that specifications, standards and construction regulations as drivers of good standard of construction are suffused with a lot of challenges (Fadason, Danladi & Jatau, 2017)

The Construction Industry in Nigeria is a collection of loosely integrated sub-sectors that collectively construct, alter and repair buildings and civil engineering works. The uniqueness of the industry is derived from the type of physical products, demands patterns, novelty and varying site conditions it operates (Andawei and Nyeke, 2021). Arguably, the Construction Industry in Nigeria is also one of the biggest employers of labour in the country after governments at the federal, state, and local levels (Nwaogu, 2018). The Industry makes a significant contribution to the country's gross capital formation and gross domestic product (National Bureau of Statistics, 2015). The Construction Industry in Nigeria is patterned after the United Kingdom Construction Industry, however,

without its diversification and advancement (Gidado, 2015).

The delivery of services and works to prospective clients in the construction Industry follows a variety of processes. It is often the case that the mostly used procurement option in the country is the traditional one or two stage method (Ogunsanmi and Bamisile, 2017). This method emphasizes the separation of the design and the construction stages of a project. Recent developments have shown the adoption of more integrated system encouraged by Value Management, Risk and Partnering which are at their infancy in the country (Babatunde et al, 2017). Projects delivered by Governments at all levels (Federal, states and local governments) in Nigeria have suffered set back due to lack of adequate inclusion and rigorous consultation with major stakeholders amidst other factors such poor choice of location, improper needs analysis, project imposition, lack of financial analysis, wrong choice of procurement route, inadequate social analysis and corruption (Hanachor, 2012; Ingwe et al., 2012). Projects like the Tinapa Business Resort, Calabar ((Eja and Eni, 2014) and Eyo C. (2011)); The Gateway International Market, Owode Yewa (Punch, 2012), Gateway International Market, Sagamu are examples of projects where inadequate consultations with key stakeholders at inception have led to near failure of the projects after delivery. Other projects were not delivered at all as they fall under the category of abandoned projects (Ingwe et al, 2012).

Statement of the Problem

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Every development project is designed and planned with a systematic arrangement that has times and schedules for commencement, duration and completion. A good planning of activities for a development project results in timely completion but when these processes for timeliness are abused, projects are subjected to abandonment and may create socio-economic and environmental issues which poses negative externalities on the general public. There are many abandoned development projects scattered across the country including Enugu State and Enugu urban in particular. Many researchers have advanced reasons for such abandonment to include change in government policy, inflation, lack of feasibility study.

The issues of housing projects abandonment in Nigeria and other developing nations of the world are persistent indicators such as project delay and sick projects abound in the continent Dumo, (2017). There are laws and regulation guiding contract executions, the pertinent questions that need to be asked and answered; can such laws, rules, regulations and other statutory provisions or any improvements to them, help to prevent and avoid this catastrophe from recurring in the future or help protect the rights and interests of the parties involved as well as impeding environmental catastrophe (Dharmasegaran, 2016). Knowing that, development project is designed and planned with a systematic arrangement that has times and schedules for commencement, duration and completion. A good planning of activities for a development project results in timely

completion but when these processes for timeliness are abused, projects are subjected to abandonment and may create socio-economic and environmental issues which poses negative externalities on the general public. One of the major causes of building and Construction project abandonments in Nigeria is cost and time overruns, and poor quality control (Olalusi & Otunola, 2022) and the same situations was obtainable in Egypt Construction Industry, until Value management (VM) was introduced and used in reducing the gap between the estimated/planned time and actual time and cost of residential constructional projects implementation, especially in the completion of 3343 housing units in the new housing complex in Helwan and Mansheyet Nasser Housing Project in Enugu urban (Khodeir & Ghandour, 2019).

The reverse is the case in Nigerian, where the irony is that in spite of this growth, the landscape is regrettably littered with abandoned building projects. Several construction projects which would have impacted positively on the economic and overall social development of the nation litters the corners and open spaces of the company (Olabusi, Otunola, 2012). Value management will help in the establishment of measures to ensure that cost and time overruns are controlled during the procurement processes from conception stage to decommissioning, Risk Management processes involves risk identification and analysis in order to ensure that the value gained during the value planning

Aim and Objectives.

The aim of this research is to evaluate the building project abandonment in Enugu urban. Specifically, this study seeks to:

1. To identify the cumulative factors responsible for public building projects abandonment in Enugu urban.
2. To assess the challenges of construction project abandonment in the Nigerian Construction industry

Research Questions:

This research question is tailored to achieve its objectives.

1. What are the cumulative factors responsible for public building projects abandonment in Enugu urban.
2. What are the challenges of construction project abandonment in the Nigerian Construction industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

CONCEPTUAL LITERATURES

Concept of Project

By definition, a project can be considered to be a series of coordinated activities and tasks embarked upon by organizations, with clearly defined objectives, commencement date, duration, requirements for resources and also funding limits. A project is delivered to quality and time and cost specifications and in order to realize them, proper organization of resources is crucial (nwankwo, 2006). This need for proper organization of resources informs the concept of

project management. According to the United Nations industrial development organization (unido), a project is a proposal for an investment to create and develop certain facilities in order to increase the production of goods and services in a community during a certain period of time. Development appraisal is carried out to examine the dimensions of a project with a view to assessing and questioning proposals before resources are committed.

imaga, igwe and nwoji (2005) define project as a scientifically evolved work plan devised to achieve a specific objective within a specified period of time for ofori, (2013), a project is a complex, nonroutine, one-time effort limited by time, budget, resources and performance specifications designed to meet customer needs. While project has several definitions, a simple and relatively inclusive one is that a project is a sequence of tasks performed to achieve a unique goal within a specific time frame. Uniqueness is the key word. It is what separates projects from operations and what makes them more difficult to manage. To standardize further on the definition of the word, the project management institute (2008) in its project management body of knowledge (pmbok) guide defines a project as a temporary endeavour undertaken to create a unique value or service. morris, (2014). View projects as characterized by general attributes such as the purpose, life cycle, uniqueness, interdependencies and conflicts. Project management is the planning, directing and controlling of organization's resources for a relatively short-term objective that has been

established to complete specific goals and objectives. For this paper project is viewed as a related set of tasks planned, performed and coordinated to achieve a specific objective or output at a given location within a limited scarce resource and period of time.

Concept of Project Abandonment

According to olalusi and otunola (2012) and ubani and ononuju (2013), abandoned projects refer to projects that have started at an earlier date, but which the construction works for one reason or the other have stopped. In order word, it means projects in which some money had been spent and the physical work had stopped before. Yap, (2013) defined abandoned project as: any project stopped at the construction stage before commissioning or any previously commissioned and used public property currently in a state of disrepair or obsolete or any project that is not being utilized for any purpose that gives value or create utility to the people. The development projects are classified as abandoned when the expected activities to be performed for the completion of the development is stopped because of many difficulties surrounding the development. Yap, (2013) argued that the projects abandonment result from the following: lack of contractors' competencies; lack of the client competencies; lack of understanding of risk and liability assessment; lack of the end users' needs and the end users-imposed restrictions on the project development.

Despite the gravity of the effects of abandoned projects, there is a lack of research in this area. It has been discovered that existing literature on

this subject is limited to the types of sources such as unpublished thesis, conference papers and particularly journals. The types of projects discussed in these sources are mainly housing or building projects, drainage, and construction projects. this may be as a result of greater number of abandoned housing projects and the fact that it has greater immediate effects to the general public (Yap, 2013). Project development particularly infrastructural projects are intended to provide new products and services to the community and at the time promote the beauty of the environment, but these advantages are underestimated and unattained because of its continuous abandonment (Ayodele and Alabi, 2011).

Causative Factors of Building Project Abandonment.

Abandoned building projects can be described as the project that has started at an earlier date, but which the construction work for one reason or the other has stopped and such are not limited to buildings alone; it can include roads, industrial structures, bridges, dams, electricity, communication projects (Olalusi & Otunola, 2012). Studies by Kolawole (2006), have shown that a good number of Construction project initiated with good intentions are abandoned at different stages of the design and construction process in Enugu State and Nigeria in general. Some reasons advanced by Makalah (2008) and Oyelola (2010) for failed construction projects in Nigeria are: incorrect estimation; lack of skilled personnel; inadequate planning; poor risk management; misunderstanding of the work

requirement; poor quality control by regulatory agencies; corruption and communication gap among the personnel. Other factors are cost; the developer and the contractors; inability of clients to engage contractors or designers capability to do the work; failure on the part of contractors to obtain vital inputs such as materials, manpower and machines.

On the other hand, Dawodu (2007), sees abandoned projects as a project in which all activities are totally suspended. While, Akindoyemi (2005) observed that a project is never considered totally abandoned, rather the project must have been suspended as a result of some of these causative factors which are: 1) the proprietor's lack of funds; 2) Inconsistent government policies; 3) lack of accountability; 4) high level of corruption; 5) incompetent contractors; 6) nonavailability of building materials; 7) lack of utilities or infrastructural facilities; 8) wrong location. The above reasons invariably leads to waste of resources in the form of capital, material, human power, promotion of illegal activities, adverse effect on community and aesthetics. Hence Rwelamila and Lobelo (2000)], advocated that construction firms should inculcate operational, strategic, personal, technological, marketing and environmental strategies in order to cushion the effect of financial predicament associated with project abandonment. Project abandonment is not restricted to Nigeria or developing countries only; "abandonment is a well-known concept on construction projects in global construction industry (! Hicks, 2008). It generally arises in

different situations. One example is when the project's design is so deficient that the contractor performs a massive amount of change orders and extra work. "The socio-economic effect of abandoned projects is overwhelming when considering the huge amount of money and resources on the part of the client has been invested.

Adequate planning, feasibility, viability and effective monitoring of financial outlay for construction projects should be put in place by various agencies concerned to reduce instances of project abandonment. Construction works involving huge capital outlay are prone to being forced to remain in the shelf for long as there is simply no cash in sight for people to buy. The Government agencies through her numerous inconsistent policies, consultants and selection procedures are pointers to abandonment of housing projects that litters the whole country. Provision of infrastructural facilities before, during and after the completion of housing project is very important to forestall abandonment. The continued neglect of on-going projects of previous governments by newly elected governments without considering the importance's of such project to National development. Many factors accounted for this, ranging from errors in pre-qualification and procurement procedure, to misappropriation of finance to incompetent consultants.

There are several factors affecting project implementation process, which invariably result in construction projects abandonment and these have been discussed from different perspectives

by different authors. Metzger (1983) listed some of them as: Poor planning, undefined contract, unstable problem definition, inexperienced management, political pressure, ineffective change control and unrealistic deadline. In the views of this author, the successful project implementation may depend to an extent on careful regulation of these factors: Insufficient capital Inflation Poor planning Political pressures and Government Bureaucracy Contractor competence and organization Variation of project scope and design Changes in consultancy service providers Change in the original design Business/Geographical environment Project complexity. There is a tendency for successive governments to discontinue projects initiated by their predecessors (Fubera, 2005). Rather than do this, the new regimes prefer to start their own projects altogether. A major reason for this is that many contracts are awarded to serve political purposes and so continue to be credited to the regime that awarded it, even if they did not complete it. Again, because many contracts are actually inflated, rather than continue to fund ongoing projects, successive governments tend to use this knowledge to discredit past governments in order to score political points. This has led to a dive in confidence in the public sector, such that funding partners approach long term public sector projects with a lot of caution. (Nwachukwu, 2008). This greatly erodes the operation of public-private funding partnerships. Sometimes, this lack of continuity derives from more sincere reasons like inflation,

which affects the cost of raw materials and changes the amount of money required to complete a project by many orders of magnitude. For projects which have been going on for a long time, several cost variations may be occasioned by this, which greatly increases the temptation to abandon them.

Nature, Causes and Effects of Project Abandonment

Tamonu and Otto (2000) posit that a project is termed abandoned when the expected completion time or period elapses and some of the physical features are seen wearing out and becoming out of use, such that will attract cost for replacement. There are two time lags, the short-term projects which run between one to two years and long-term projects which run between three to five years, as applicable. If a project is not completed within the scheduled time even when extra time and additional resources are added, it is termed to be abandoned. Dawodu (1987) sees abandoned projects as that in which all activities are totally suspended. Akindoyemi's (2005) opinion deferred a bit, as he postulate that a project is never considered abandoned, rather the project must have been suspended as a result of the proprietor lacking funds to continue in the main time.

Kolawole (2006) asserts that a good number of projects initiated with good intentions are abandoned at different stages of the design and construction process. Oyelola (2010) and Makalah (2008) state that the reasons for failed projects are: incorrect estimation; lack of skilled

personnel; inadequate planning; poor risk management; misunderstanding of the work requirement; poor quality control by regulatory agencies; corruption and communication gap among the personnel.

Adeleke (2005) declares that conflicting government policies, lack of accountability, high level of corruption, unskilled contractors, inadequate building materials, infrastructural deficit, and wrong choice of facility location and so on has been advanced as some of the major causes of abandonment of projects.

Imaga, (2003) and Hanachor (2012) highlight the causes of project abandonment as follows:

(a) Political Reasons: Most projects are political projects that were not originally meant to be completed. They were initiated merely to score some political points. Because of the reason for selecting such projects, proper feasibility studies of the project are not carried out (Imaga, 2003). For reasons of tribal political patronage, sensitive projects are mostly awarded to unqualified contractors or to political zones where the project would never survive in order to compensate for political support given from those areas. This automatically breeds inefficiency of such projects and eventually abandoned (Hanachor, 2012).

(b) Corruption: Globally, Nigeria ranks high as one of the most corrupt nations of the world. Many projects are abandoned either because the funds made available for it are embezzled or because those whose duty it is to provide funds for its completion are not interested in doing so because they cannot get their “kick-back”. Even

when old projects are abandoned, new ones are started because of the changes of getting “kick-backs” from the new (Imaga, 2003). Most contractors in order to win the contract, deliberately lowers their quotation, only to apply for variation later. Some who may go on with the project will resort to the use of inferior materials or even deviate from the original project plan (Hanachor, 2012).

(c) Inflation: The inflationary trend in Nigeria, as in many other developing countries defies economic prediction. This makes it difficult for projects to be adequately estimated (Imaga, 2003).

(d) Poor Feasibility Report: The essence of a feasibility report is to know the viability or non-viability of a project, but in some cases feasibility reporters are influenced to give positive reports for even obvious non-viable projects. This affects real implementation of the projects (Imaga, 2003). Most projects usually require counterpart funding but when one or more parties to the funding fails the resultant effect will be insufficient funds for the project. Therefore, the project will definitely be abandoned (Hanachor, 2012).

(e) Lack of Accountability: The lack of accountability makes projects managers and politicians feel that they can do whatever they like with the project. If there is the culture of accountability those who mismanage projects will be blacklisted in society, thereby improving on the efficiency of project execution (Imaga, 2003).

(f) Appointment of mediocre Project Managers:

When inexperienced project managers are appointed there is the tendency of project abandonment. When mediocre or inexperienced project managers are appointed, they hardly understand the rudiments of project management. The result is that either extra fund is needed while trying to complete the project or project is abandoned outright (Imaga, 2003). Most projects require technical inputs which must be attended to by experts. Where this aspect is not taken into consideration and the local crafts men are not able to handle it, the project would be put to a halt (Hanachor, 2012).

(g) Choice of Project site or Location: The choice of the site is very important. Since the host community must of necessity be the custodian of the project, consensus must be reached on where the project is to be sited before embarking on it. Rifts between the host communities and project managers most times creates chaotic business atmosphere which leads to destruction of materials and eventual abandonment of the project. In some cases, project facilities are located far from the source of raw materials which leads to ineffective performance and eventual abandonment. To achieve the desired result, the major stakeholders in the community such as the chiefs, youths, women and development stakeholders or beneficiaries need be consulted on the choice of the project site (Hanachor, 2012).

Project abandonment negatively affects the level of economic growth and development of Nigeria.

Gregory (2007:112) views economic growth as the increasing capacity of the economy to satisfy the wants of its members. Economic growth is enabled by increases in productivity, which lowers the inputs (labor, capital, material, energy, etc.) Claire, Renate and Ursula (2011) state that economic growth has the indirect potential to alleviate poverty, as a result of a simultaneous increase in employment opportunities. Growth process increases labor productivity, effective and efficient utilization of human, financial and material resources. Increases in employment without corresponding increases in productivity leads to a rise in the number of "working poor". This is why some experts are now promoting the creation of "quality" and not "quantity" in labor market policies.

Abandonment of projects obviously leads to waste of resources in the form of capital, material, human power, promotion of illegal activities, adverse effect on community, aesthetics and so on. Hence, Rwelamila and Lobelo (2000) advocate that firms should inculcate operational, strategic, personal, technological, marketing and environmental strategies in order to cushion the effect of financial predicament associated with project abandonment. Elrufai (2012:1), states that there are eleven thousand, eight hundred and eighty-six (11,886) abandoned projects that will cost an estimated N7.78 trillion to complete. These alarming figures are from the report of the Presidential Projects Assessment Committee (PPAC) set up in March 2011, by President

Goodluck Jonathan to look into cases of abandoned federal government projects. If the government does not start any new projects, it will take more than five years budgeting about N1.5 trillion annually to complete them all – and that is assuming no cost-over runs or delays. This colossal waste of financial resources would have contributed in no small measure towards improving the economy of the country.

The main reason for a development project is to create positive change in the community by empowering the individuals economically and socially. A positive change process should lead to a further change in other aspects (Thompson 1983). When development projects are abandoned, the community members and beneficiaries are automatically robbed of the expected changes and consequently leave them worse than they were before the project.

Imaga (2003:288) highlights the effect of project abandonment on the economy to include: Enormous waste of scarce resources, low economic growth rates, low income per capital, technological backwardness and failure syndrome.

Imaga (2003) notes that the human and material resources expended on a project is wasted when the project is abandoned. This reduces the rate of economic development. The production rate is reduced and this in effect will lead to a reduction in the nation's per capita income (income per head). Low per capita income results in low standard of living of the people. Some projects are very crucial for technological advancement that when such projects are abandoned, it keeps

the country in technological prison and backward.

Oyeola (2010:32) notes that when government projects in communities are abandoned, the community member go as far as vandalizing the material and whatever is left in the site at that time. On return to site, after years of abandonment, the vandalized materials have to be replaced at extra cost. Sometimes the governments end up re-awarding the contract to new contractor at even a more contract value than at first.

Ways to Control Incessant Project Abandonment in Nigeria

In other to avert the likelihood of development projects being abandoned, there is need for project analysis, evaluation and monitoring. Desai (2010) notes that project analysis is the articulation of the various dimensions of a project life cycle, both separately and in relation to each other. In his view, a multidimensional project analysis should cover the following areas: Social analysis, institutional analysis, financial analysis, economic analysis technical analysis

Social project analysis: Social analysis of project considers the sustainability of the proposed project in line with its impact on the people. It takes care of the socio-cultural and demographic characteristics of the project population to win and hold peoples support and to achieve project goals by including changes in social attitudes and behavior.

Institutional analysis: Institutional project analysis provides a means of recognizing and partnering with local or community institutions

which if neglected results to projects being abandoned. What becomes of a development project depends on the acceptance and participation of the institutions involved in the project. The institutions comprises of the youths, chiefs, group leaders and other stakeholders.

Financial analysis: Proper financial analysis prevents abandonment of projects, irrespective of the sponsors. Financial analysis of a project takes cognizance of the cost of the project and the source or sources of the funds. In the case of government project, the stages and the amount to release at each stage of the project should be made known and monitored. It is necessary for the government to adequately fund projects, monitor what has been done and ensure the completion of abandoned projects before awarding new ones.

Economic analysis: Economic analysis of a project explains how resources are sourced and effectively utilized. It seeks to determine not only the use of the project, but also whether there is any other alternative way of getting the same value, the proposed project will offer. Economic analysis entails a comparison of costs and benefits with or without the project, in terms of their opportunity cost to the community or donor agencies in the best alternative uses. Economic analysis will ensure that projects will never lose its value within a short time.

Technical analysis: Technical project analysis considers the technological requirement of a project and the possible sources. There are usually two sources, the local skill and technology or the imported technology.

Depending on the type of project to be executed, the technical analysis will suggest most appropriate way of carrying out the project. Technical analysis will specify the types of professionals required for the project and when or at what stage they will be involved. There should be proper monitoring and evaluation of the pace and level of work done at each stage to ensure adequate completion of project phases.

Theoretical Literature

Transformation theory

In the construction system, production takes inputs in the form of labour, materials, finance, information, plants and equipment, and converts them into the expected services and products, otherwise known as outputs. The principles of a classical transformation include (i) the division of production into smaller controllable sub-processes and further into tasks, then making available all the inputs required for a particular work section and then allocating these tasks to workers; (ii) the reduction of the project cost by minimising each cost of the sub process; and (iii) linking of the input value of a process with the output value (Gao, 2013). In practice, the value of a finished building can be increased using skilled labour, better materials and effective task management (Gao, 2013). This theory is particularly relevant to BPM because it explains the need to define works required to deliver a construction project, which helps to avoid unnecessary efforts.

Empirical Review

Ejaz, (2023) in their study on assessment of most critical success factors for mega construction

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projects in Pakistan, identified five (5) factors as key drivers for the success of construction projects. Survey method with the aid of questionnaires was used to elicit responses from professionals in the industry. Descriptive statistics viz, mean score ranks were used to analyse the results. The findings from the study include planning efforts and scheduling, adequate funding, ability of the project manager to decision, adequate planning and specification, timely decision making by client.

Omran, (2022) did a study on evaluation of factors for success of construction projects in Wadi Alhaya, Libya using questionnaire survey to elicit information from 44 respondents. The findings from the study after using relative importance index revealed that ten (10) factors were critical to the realization of success of construction projects. They include contractor's experience, project manager's leadership skills, labour productivity, quality relationship between team members, shortage of materials etc.

Poon et al. (2021) did a study on the identification of success factors in the construction process using literature review in arriving at their findings. The findings from the study include clearly defined project objectives, scope of the project, the project manager, project team, planning, and control, appropriate size of work package, communication and information management, top management support as well as environmental health and safety.

Ogwueleka, (2021) did a study on critical factors of success influencing project performance in

Nigeria. Five (5) factors were identified as key drivers. The study adopted the survey method where 188 questionnaires were distributed to the respondents in the four regions of Nigeria. Frequency, severity and importance index were used to analyse the results from the study. The findings revealed objective management, management of design, technical factors, top management's support and risk management as key drivers to success.

Baccarini and Collins (2023) studied factors critical to the success of projects in Australia. The study adopted a survey method using questionnaire to elicit responses from one hundred and fifty (150) respondents. Descriptive statistics viz frequency distribution was used to analyse the data. The findings revealed that project's understanding, competent project team, communication, realistic schedule and cost estimates as well as adequate project control seems to be key drivers to successful projects.

Yong and Mustaffa (2022) attempted to study the principal factors that are critical to the success of construction projects in Malaysia. Using a questionnaire as a means of data collection and mean score analysis, 15 key factors were identified as a means of delivering construction projects to fruition from a response of about 45 questionnaires. The factors include financial capability of the client, control of contractor's work, consultant's competence, consultant's ability to solve problems, etc.

Chase, Acquilano and Jacobs (2022) describe a project as a series of related jobs usually requiring a significant period of time to perform.

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Project management is therefore seen as, the planning, directing and controlling of resources (people, equipment and material) to meet the technical, cost, and time constraints of the project. Imaga (2023) assert that while project is a capital investment to develop facilities to provide goods and services, project abandonment means any project that is not completed on schedule and whose implementation does not continue thereafter. Project abandonment is therefore, the giving up or discontinuation of a project which has taken off (mid-stream).

In a critique by Mazi Jetson Nwakwo (2024), acting managing director of the NRC, he pointed out that the rail system is suffering from lack of political will by the nation's politicians. While the NRC had employed about 45,000 people between 1954 and 1975, current employment is only 6,516. He stated that the old wagons acquired since 1993 are still being used without significant replacements or acquisition of modern ones, and some wagons date back to 1948. The condition of the track limit trains to a speed of 35 km/h.

Elrufai (2022) states that one of the major reasons given for project abandonment is lack of funds. Then, one wonders how funding constraints can be blamed for project failures. Should one not also wonder why a project is approved in the absence of adequate funds? Section 4 (2) (b) of the Public Procurement Act 2007, states plainly that all procurement shall be „based only on procurement plans supported by prior budgetary appropriations; and no

procurement dealings shall be formalized until the procuring body has ensured that funds are available to meet the obligations and has obtained a “Certificate of „No Objection“ to Contract Award” from the Agency“. Therefore, it is specified that no contract should be awarded if funds are not available for it from the onset.

Makalah (2018) describe project abandonment as structures on which taxes and mortgages are no longer paid, and for which services are neither paid for nor provided. Such structures are unoccupied, vandalized, deteriorated or unmaintained. Generally, abandonment can mean an owner ceasing to provide maintenance and operating services to a building, or the loss of an owner’s legal right to a building, or the demolition of a building or any form of structure. An abandoned project is an uncompleted project within in a time frame of the contract. There are two dimensions to project. The tangible and the non-tangible projects. This study will focus on the tangible dimension, which results to the execution of physical projects that brightens the community. Physical projects results to empowerment, self-improvement and positively impacts on the economy.

Abandoned projects as in building and civil engineering like: houses, churches, schools, roads, railways, bridges, dams, tunnels, airport, sea port etc. litter across the whole Nigeria. Osemenan (2017) reports that Nigeria has become the “world’s junk-yard” of abandoned projects worth billions of naira. This is greatly unthinkable that Nigeria blessed with great potentials in the construction industry can

experience such magnitude of project abandonment. In another report by Kotangora (2023) there are about 4000 uncompleted or abandoned project belonging to the Federal Government of Nigeria with an estimated cost of above N 300 billion which will take 30 years to complete at the present execution capacity of government. The issue of project abandonment has been left without adequate attention for too long which is now having a multiplier effect on both the construction industry and the national economy.

Olapade and Anthony (2022) reveal that abandoned projects in Nigeria will cost an estimated N7.78 trillion to complete. These abandoned projects cut across all sectors including Health, Education and Transport, especially the Nigerian Railway Corporation (NRC). This study centers on the Nigerian Railway Corporation whose activities, programmes and projects have been relegated to the background. This is adjudged to be due to myriads of socio-economic and political factors inhibiting its continued operation in spite of its invaluable contribution to the Nigerian economy.

Research Design

The survey research design was used for the study. According to Left Wich (2013), a survey research is that type of study in which a sample is selected randomly from the study population and studied, and the results are used to make generalization on the matter investigated. Thus, the researcher considered this design appropriate because original data from the

respondents will be collected and analysed and it will be generalized to be representative of the entire population.

Population for the Study

Population is defined as the total collection of elements about which we wish to make inferences (Cooper & Schindler, 2003). Mugenda and Mugenda, (2003), explain that the target population should have some observable characteristics, to which the researcher intends to generalize the results of the study. The researcher narrowed the sample observation to consultants, contractors and clients in Enugu urban for feasibility reasons, the target population of this study shall be 50 registered contractors in Enugu urban, 45 Engineers and 150 clients, which summed up to 245 respondents.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

A sample size was determined from a total population of 245 respondents using the Nauom (2007). Stratified random sampling technique was used to select the respondents. Stratified random sampling technique ensures that different groups of a population are adequately represented in the sample. In this section of sampling design, the researcher mainly strategies related to sampling techniques for easy access to right data from respondents. The process of deriving the sample and the technique used is referred to as sampling technique. A scientific means or statistical tools where used to determine the sample size of the study. Nauom (2007) used this formula for finite population as

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where: n= Desired sample size

N= the entire population

e= level of significance or limit of tolerable error assumed to be 5% or 0.05

I= unit, constant figure

Therefore:

For contractors

$$N = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{50}{1 + 50(0.05)^2} = 50$$

$$n = \frac{50}{1 + 50(0.0025)} = 44$$

n= 44

For clients

$$N = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{150}{1 + 150(0.05)^2} = 150$$

$$n = \frac{150}{1 + 150(0.0025)} = 109$$

For Consultant

$$N = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{45}{1 + 45(0.05)^2} = 45$$

$$n = \frac{45}{1 + 45(0.0025)} = 40$$

Table 3.2 Estimated Population Distribution and Sample Size of the Study

S/N	CATEGORIES OF RESPONDENTS	ESTIMATED POPULATION	SAMPLE SIZE
1.	Contractor	50	44
2.	Client/public	150	109
3.	Engineers	45	40
	TOTAL	245	193

Source: Field Survey (2024).

ANALYSES OF THE FIRST RESEARCH QUESTION

What are the cumulative factors responsible for public building projects abandonment in Enugu urban.

Table 5.2

S/No	RiskFactors affecting labour productivity	SA 1	A 2	UD 3	D 4	SD 5	ΣFX	INDEX	RANK
1	Lack of fund	25 25	28 56	30 90	40 160	52 260	175 591	3.37	1
2	Inconsistent government policies	27 27	30 60	35 105	43 172	40 200	175 564	3.22	2

3	Lack of accountabilities	29 29	31 62	37 111	44 176	34 170	175 548	3.13	3
4	High level of corruption	30 30	32 64	40 120	45 180	28 140	175 534	3.05	4
5	Incompetent contractors	32 32	34 68	43 129	48 192	18 90	175 511	2.92	5
6	Non availability of building materials	33 33	36 72	45 135	48 192	13 65	175 497	2.84	6
7	Lack of utilities	35 35	36 72	48 144	50 200	6 30	175 481	2.74	7
8	Wrong materials	37 37	37 74	49 147	50 200	2 10	175 468	2.67	8
9	Lack of infrastructural facilities	40 40	35 70	48 144	50 200	2 10	175 469	2.66	9
10	Poor planning	42 42	36 72	49 147	48 192		175 453	2.58	10
11	Undefined contracts	44 44	35 70	46 136	47 188	3 15	175 453	2.58	11
12	Inexperienced management	44 44	36 72	46 136	47 188	2 5	175 445	2.54	12
13	Political pressure	46 46	40 80	40 120	46 184	3 15	175 445	2.54	13
14	Unrealistic deadline	47 47	41 82	40 120	43 172	4 20	175 441	2.52	14
15	Ineffective change control	49 49	40 80	40 120	40 160	6 30	175 439	2.50	15
	Grand Mean							2.79	

Table 5.2 above shows that the cumulative factors responsible for public project abandonment in Enugu urban includes lack of fund, inconsistent government policies, lack of accountabilities, high level of corruption,

incompetent contractors, non-availability of building materials, lack of utilities, wrong materials, lack of infrastructural facilities, poor planning and undefined contracts. The study further indicates that the lack of fund has the

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highest index of 3.37, followed by inconsistent government policies which has the index of 3.22, this is followed by lack of accountability which has the index of 3.13, high level of corruption has the index of 3.05, incompetent contractors has the index of 2.92, followed by non-availability of building materials with an index of 2.84. Lack of utilities has the index of 2.74, wrong materials have an index of 2.67, and lack of infrastructural

facilities has an index of 2.66. This is followed by poor planning which has an index of 2.58, undefined contract has index of 2.58, inexperienced management has an index of 2.54, and political pressure has an index of 2.54. Followed by unrealistic deadline which has an index of 2.52. Finally, ineffective change control has an index of 2.50.

ANALYSES OF THE SECOND RESEARCH QUESTION

What are the challenges of construction project abandonment in the Nigerian Construction industry.

Table 5.3

S/N		W	SA-----				ΣFX	\bar{X}	DECISION
			SD	4	3	2			
1	It reveals the level of technical knowledge	F WF	80 320	65 195	15 30	10 10	175 555	3.17	ACCEPT
2	It promotes corruption and embezzlement of public/private fund	F WF	85 340	60 180	13 26	17 17	175 563	3.21	ACCEPT
3	Loss of asset utilization	F WF	79 316	58 174	18 36	20 20	175 546	3.12	ACCEPT
4	Loss of finance	F WF	66 264	77 231	20 40	12 12	175 547	3.12	ACCEPT
5	It discourages innovation	F WF	59 236	79 237	16 32	21 21	175 526	3.00	ACCEPT

6	It encourages risk transfer	F WF	63 252	71 213	19 38	22 22	175 525	3.00	ACCEPT
7	Grand Total							3.10	ACCEPT

From this study, the mean value of all the identified factors are above 2.5 benchmark indicating that the challenges of construction project abandonment in the Nigerian construction industry the level of technical knowledge, it promotes corruption and embezzlement of public/private fund, loss of asset utilization, loss of finance, it discourages innovation and encourages risk transfer.

The result further explains that the identified challenges of construction project abandonment in the Nigerian construction industry are as follows; (i) it reveals the level of technical knowledge with a mean rate of 3.17; (ii) It promotes corruption and embezzlement of public/private fund with a mean rate of 3.21; (iii) loss of asset utilization with a mean rate of 3.12; (iv) Loss of finance with a mean rate of 3.12; (v) it discourages innovation with a mean rate of 3.00; (vi) it encourages risk transfer with a mean rate of 3.00. Hence, the researcher concludes that the identified factors are the challenges of construction project abandonment in the Nigerian construction industry.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher hereby concludes that the identified factors such as lack of fund, inconsistent government policies, lack of accountability and many more

are the factors responsible for public building project abandonment in Enugu urban. More so, the study concludes that the challenges of construction project abandonment in the Nigerian construction industry ranges from it reveals the technical knowledge; it promotes corruption and embezzlement of public/private fund and many more. Furthermore, the study concludes that integrated and risk management have significant effect on the mitigation of risk factor. Finally, the study concludes that the level of applicability of integrated value and risk management as a strategy for mitigating abandonment of construction project in Enugu urban are low.

Recommendations for further studies.

This research as earlier stated serves as a precursor for more researches in this field of study. Therefore, this research recommends that further studies should:

1. There is need for government and relevant stakeholder in the industries to enforce the application of integrated value and risk management in order to reduce/minimize the rate of project abandonment in Nigeria specifically in Enugu urban.
2. There is need for stakeholders in the building construction industries to assess the identified challenges of building construction

that leads to project abandonment in the construction industries and enhances the stability/suitability of the sector for proper building management.

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